

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
5

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles

PUBLISHED EVERY MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS

**PROFESSORS-TEACHERS, SPECIALISTS
AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHERS.**

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 94 3540880

<https://econoscitech-integration-journal.uz>

2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich
Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor,

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich
doctor of economics (DSC), professor

RESPONSIBLE SECRETARY:

Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li
TSUE independent researcher

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 5. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on May, 2026.

Editorial Board Members:

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Said Irandoust,
Doctor of Chemical Engineering Sciences,
Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich,
Doctor of Economics, (DSc), Professor

Tokunaga Masahiro,
professor, PhD of Economics of the Faculty of
Business and Commerce

Debasis Das,
professor Department of Computer Science

Nitin Goje,
professor and Program Lead - Computer Science

Nargizakhon Shamshieva
Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Rakhmonov Norim Razzakovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Bayxonov Bahodirjon Tursunbayevich
Doctor of Science (DSc), Professor

Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich,
PhD, Associate Professor

Boymuratov Abduraxmat Djumayevich
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics

Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna
DSc, Associate Professor

Sultanova Kamila Mukhtorali Kizi
Master of Science

CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсуфов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadiilloyevna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPSIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES:	

A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ)	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS	253
Baymuradov Shokhruxh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION)	259

Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	
MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ.....	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	

THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	
COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohruzbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
ISSUES OF IMPROVING PRE-TRIAL TAX DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	439
Solihova Xumora Xasan kizi	
INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN COMPANIES.....	446
Akmal Komiljonovich Shermukhamedov	
COMMUNITY-BASED HERITAGE TOURISM MODELS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING HANDICRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	451
Olimjonova Farog‘at Dilmurod qizi	
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ОПЫТ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	458
Шоахмедов Шоҳрух Шорахимович	

OF EFFECTIVE USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND	464
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich	
ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION	469
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich	
DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS	473
Nurmukhammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	
ESG INTEGRATION PRACTICES INTO CORPORATE CULTURE SYSTEM IN THE JOINTSTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: A CASE STUDY OF “DORI-DARMON” JSC.....	479
Sadikova Muslima Alisher kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET IN THE TASHKENT REGION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT	485
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	491
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	497
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	503
Isroilov Madaminjon Mukhsinovich	
FEATURES OF SUMMARIZING AND EVALUATING THE RESULTS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT AUDITING IN UZBEKISTAN PRACTICE	509
Isroil Ismoilovich Meliev	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ФИНАНСАМИ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ РЕФА С ДИСТРИБУТИВНЫМ АНАЛИЗОМ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОДХОДА SEQ.....	516
Зокиржонов Мухаммадсодик Равшанбек угли	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	530
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS IN AQUACULTURE CLUSTERS: IFRS INTEGRATION, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG PERSPECTIVES.....	537
Shodiev Aslam Rahmatilloevich	
APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PREDICTING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	544
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas	
SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION UNDER WATER SCARCITY: GLOBAL EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN	550
Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna	

SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION UNDER WATER SCARCITY: GLOBAL EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN

Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna
Researcher, Bukhara State University
E-mail: nigorasadykova667@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0003-7499-7958

Abstract. This article investigates how regional specialization can be redesigned under conditions of chronic water scarcity. It integrates classical comparative advantage theory, location theory, new economic geography, cluster development, institutional economics, and smart specialization with water stress, water footprint, virtual water, and water productivity approaches. The study applies systemic, comparative, structural, and institutional analysis to examine international experience from Israel, Australia, the Netherlands, and Spain, and relates the findings to Uzbekistan, with particular attention to the Bukhara region. The results demonstrate that sustainable specialization in water-constrained territories should not be evaluated solely by output volume or historical production patterns. Instead, it should be guided by value added, employment, export earnings, and ecological effects per cubic metre of water. The article proposes a diversified smart specialization model for Bukhara based on water-efficient horticulture, greenhouse production, food processing, tourism, education, digital services, and water technologies. Institutional reforms, digital water accounting, differentiated incentives, research–business cooperation, and strict monitoring are identified as prerequisites for effective implementation.

Keywords: regional specialization, water scarcity, water productivity, virtual water, water footprint, smart specialization, regional development, Bukhara region.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются направления устойчивого развития территориальной специализации в условиях хронического дефицита водных ресурсов. Теоретическая основа исследования объединяет концепции сравнительных преимуществ, размещения производства, новой экономической географии, кластерного развития, институциональной экономики и умной специализации с подходами водного стресса, водного следа, виртуальной воды и продуктивности воды. На основе системного, сравнительного, структурного и институционального анализа изучен опыт Израиля, Австралии, Нидерландов и Испании, а полученные выводы адаптированы к условиям Узбекистана, особенно Бухарской области. Установлено, что при выборе отраслевых приоритетов необходимо учитывать не только объём производства, но и добавленную стоимость, занятость, экспортную выручку и экологический эффект в расчёте на один кубический метр воды. Для Бухарской области предложена диверсифицированная модель умной специализации, основанная на водосберегающем садоводстве, тепличном хозяйстве, переработке пищевой продукции, туризме, образовании, цифровых услугах и водных технологиях. Институциональные реформы, цифровой учёт воды, дифференцированные стимулы, сотрудничество науки и бизнеса, а также строгий мониторинг определены в качестве необходимых условий эффективной реализации данной модели.

Ключевые слова: территориальная специализация, дефицит воды, продуктивность воды, виртуальная вода, водный след, умная специализация, региональное развитие, Бухарская область.

INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity is a structural economic constraint. Population growth, climate variability, urbanisation, and rising food demand are increasing pressure on limited freshwater resources. Consequently, regional policy must assess not only output and employment, but also the value created per unit of water.

Regional specialization is one of the central categories of regional economics. It explains how territories concentrate resources and capabilities in activities in which they possess relative advantages. Classical interpretations emphasised natural resources, labour productivity, and market access. Contemporary interpretations add knowledge, innovation, institutional quality, connectivity, and entrepreneurial discovery. Under conditions of water scarcity, however, the concept requires an additional criterion: the amount of economic and social value generated per unit of water used. This criterion changes the ranking of sectors and products because activities with large gross output may generate relatively low value added and high ecological pressure, while service industries and technologically advanced agriculture can produce substantially higher returns with lower water intensity.

This issue is especially important for Central Asia, where a dry climate, irrigated agriculture, ageing infrastructure, and regional disparities interact. In Uzbekistan, water-intensive production remains economically important, yet it increases vulnerability to drought and upstream supply changes. Therefore, Bukhara needs a specialization model that combines efficient agriculture with tourism, processing industries, and knowledge-intensive services.

The purpose of this article is to develop a policy-oriented framework for sustainable regional specialization under water scarcity and to identify strategic directions for Uzbekistan and the Bukhara region. The study addresses three questions. First, how should the theory of regional specialization be modified when water becomes a binding constraint? Second, what lessons can be learned from countries that have combined water efficiency with high-value production? Third, which institutional, technological, and sectoral priorities are most relevant for Bukhara? The contribution of the article lies in integrating regional economics with water-economy indicators and formulating an adaptation model that treats water scarcity not only as a limitation, but also as a stimulus for innovation and structural change.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The intellectual foundations of regional specialization originate from the classical theory of comparative advantage. Smith and Ricardo demonstrated that territories gain from concentrating on activities in which their relative productivity is higher. Although this logic remains relevant, it is insufficient for water-constrained regions because observed productivity may ignore resource depletion, environmental impacts, and the implicit export of scarce water. A product may be commercially competitive while remaining socially inefficient when its full water cost is taken into account.

Cluster theory emphasises the geographical concentration of interconnected firms, suppliers, research organisations, and public institutions. Porter (2000) argues that clusters improve productivity, innovation, and entrepreneurship by facilitating knowledge flows and specialised services. For water-scarce regions, cluster logic suggests that isolated investment in irrigation equipment is less effective than an integrated ecosystem involving technology providers, farmers, processors, universities, financial institutions, and water authorities. Such an ecosystem can support continuous improvement in crop selection, monitoring, water reuse, and processing.

The water-stress framework of Falkenmark and Rockström (2004) classifies territories according to renewable water availability per capita. Although this indicator does not capture every local condition, it provides a clear signal of when water begins to constrain economic activity. Water-footprint analysis, developed by Hoekstra and Chapagain (2008), extends the assessment from direct withdrawals to the full volume of blue, green, and grey water embedded in products and consumption. Mekonnen and Hoekstra (2016) demonstrated the global scale of severe water scarcity and highlighted the importance of seasonal and spatial variation.

Water productivity offers an operational indicator for policy. Molden (2007) defines it in physical terms, such as kilograms per cubic metre, or in economic terms, such as value added per cubic metre. Economic water productivity is more suitable for comparing agriculture, industry, and services because it provides a common measure. Nevertheless, a complete assessment should include employment, export revenue, tax contribution, and ecological impact. This multidimensional approach avoids selecting sectors solely because they generate high monetary returns while neglecting social inclusion or environmental sustainability (Table 1).

Table 1. Main theoretical approaches to regional specialization under water scarcity

Approach	Key scholars	Core proposition	Relevance for water-scarce regions
Comparative advantage	A. Smith; D. Ricardo	Specialize according to relative resource and labour productivity	Select activities with low water intensity and high value
New economic geography	P. Krugman; M. Fujita	Market size, transport costs and agglomeration shape concentration	Assess market access jointly with water infrastructure
Cluster approach	M. Porter	Co-location of firms and institutions raises productivity and innovation	Build agro-technology, tourism and service clusters
Smart specialization	D. Foray; P. McCann	Priorities should reflect unique local capabilities and discovery	Concentrate scarce water on activities with the highest return
Institutional approach	D. Acemoglu; A. Rodríguez-Pose	Governance quality and inclusive institutions shape outcomes	Ensure transparent allocation, tariffs, monitoring and accountability

Source: Compiled by the author based on the reviewed literature.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research uses a qualitative and analytical design that combines systemic, comparative, structural, and institutional methods. The systemic method is applied to interpret regional specialization as the interaction of natural resources, production structure, infrastructure, human capital, institutions, and innovation. The comparative method is used to examine the experience of Israel, Australia, the Netherlands, and Spain. The structural method identifies the relationship between sectoral composition and water intensity. The institutional method evaluates the rules, incentives, and organisations required for effective implementation.

The principal evaluation indicator is economic water productivity, expressed conceptually as the ratio of value added generated by an activity to the volume of water consumed. For public decision-making, this indicator should be supplemented by employment per cubic metre, export revenue per cubic metre, fiscal return per cubic metre, and a qualitative environmental-risk score. Because comparable and fully disaggregated regional data are limited, this article does not present econometric estimation. Instead, it develops a policy framework based on triangulation of the academic literature, international cases, and the structural characteristics of Bukhara.

The selection of international cases follows a most-different-systems logic. Israel represents technology-intensive water reuse and drip irrigation. Australia represents tradable water entitlements and basin-level allocation. The Netherlands represents closed greenhouse systems, advanced logistics, and high agricultural value despite limited land and water resources. Spain represents a combination of irrigation modernisation, differentiated pricing, and export-oriented Mediterranean agriculture. These cases differ in geography and governance, but they all demonstrate mechanisms relevant to water-efficient specialization.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In a water-scarce economy, the shadow price of water changes comparative advantage. Activities that create more value and employment per cubic metre become preferable, while low-value water-intensive production creates opportunity costs for households, ecosystems, and higher-productivity sectors.

Israel demonstrates how technology, pricing, and institutional coordination can transform water scarcity into an innovation advantage. Drip irrigation, desalination, wastewater reuse, and precision agriculture are integrated with research institutions and export-oriented technology firms. The lesson is not that Bukhara should reproduce Israel's entire system, but that water-saving equipment should be linked to monitoring, agronomic advisory services, processing, and innovation finance.

Australia's Murray–Darling Basin experience highlights the role of clearly defined water entitlements, limits, and allocation mechanisms. Market-based instruments can help reallocate water toward higher-value users, but they require reliable measurement, enforcement, and protection of environmental flows. For Uzbekistan, the immediate lesson is the need for transparent limits and volumetric accounting before more complex allocation mechanisms are considered (Table 2).

Table 2. International mechanisms and their adaptation relevance for Bukhara

Country	Main mechanism	Priority activities	Observed strategic outcome	Lesson for Bukhara
Israel	Drip irrigation, reuse and desalination	Vegetables, flowers, agro-technology	High water productivity and technology exports	Develop a water-efficient agro-cluster and reuse systems
Australia	Water entitlements, caps and adaptive basin management	Horticulture, vineyards and high-value crops	Water shifts toward higher-value uses	Introduce reliable accounting, limits and economic incentives
Netherlands	Closed greenhouses and recirculating systems	Greenhouse vegetables and floriculture	High exports with low water use	Integrate greenhouses, science, processing and logistics
Spain	Drip irrigation, tariffs and cluster development	Olives, grapes, citrus and horticulture	Growth of export-oriented production	Restructure crops according to water productivity

Source: Compiled by the author from the comparative case analysis.

The analysis indicates that Bukhara requires diversified smart specialization. The first priority is water-efficient agriculture, including intensive horticulture, vineyards, medicinal plants, drought-resistant crops, and greenhouse production supported by drip irrigation, soil-moisture monitoring, and agronomic advisory services.

The second priority is the development of tourism and related services. Bukhara's cultural assets provide a comparative advantage that does not depend heavily on irrigation water. Sustainable tourism should include water-efficient hotels, heritage conservation, digital booking systems, local crafts, gastronomy, and professional training. A stronger link between tourism and local food processing can generate demand for high-value regional products.

Technological modernisation must be accompanied by institutional reform. District-level water-economic passports should combine water limits, land conditions, crop structure, infrastructure losses, and value-added indicators. Investment decisions should then prioritise projects that increase economic water productivity while remaining within basin limits.

Financial instruments should reward high water productivity and value added. Concessional loans, green finance, public-private partnerships, and performance-based subsidies should support metering, water reuse, efficient irrigation, cold storage, processing, and renewable energy. Support should depend on verified water savings rather than equipment purchases alone.

The overall result is a model of structural renewal rather than the abrupt abandonment of traditional sectors. Agriculture remains important, but its composition shifts from raw, water-intensive production toward efficient cultivation and processing. Industry shifts toward recycling and closed-water cycles. Services expand through tourism, education, health care, logistics, and digital exports. This combination improves resilience to drought while creating new competitive advantages.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study confirms that regional specialization under conditions of water scarcity must be assessed through a broader framework than historical production shares or gross output. Water becomes a binding economic factor that changes comparative advantage and requires the use of indicators such as value added, employment, export earnings, and environmental impact per cubic metre.

For the Bukhara region, the most appropriate pathway is a diversified smart specialization model based on water-efficient horticulture, vineyards, medicinal plants, greenhouse production, food processing, cultural tourism, education, digital services, and water technologies. This strategy should be implemented gradually and should preserve rural employment through training, finance, and improved market access.

Five recommendations are proposed: to introduce district-level water-economic passports; to link irrigation support to measured outcomes; to develop value-chain clusters for horticulture, processing, and tourism; to establish a regional water-technology platform involving universities and firms; and to publish annual indicators of water use, productivity, losses, and sectoral value added.

REFERENCES

1. Acemoglu D., Robinson J.A. *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty* / D. Acemoglu, J.A. Robinson. – New York: Crown Publishers, 2012. – 529 p.
2. Allan J.A. *Virtual Water: Tackling the Threat to Our Planet's Most Precious Resource* / J.A. Allan. – London: I.B. Tauris, 2011. – 240 p.
3. Capello R. *Regional Economics* / R. Capello. – 2nd ed. – London: Routledge, 2016. – 378 p.
4. Falkenmark M., Rockström J. *Balancing Water for Humans and Nature: The New Approach in Ecohydrology* / M. Falkenmark, J. Rockström. – London: Earthscan, 2004. – 247 p.
5. Foray D. *Smart Specialisation: Opportunities and Challenges for Regional Innovation Policy* / D. Foray. – London: Routledge, 2015. – 115 p.
6. Grafton R.Q., Williams J., Perry C.J., Molle F., Ringler C., Steduto P., Udall B., Wheeler S.A., Wang Y., Garrick D., Allen R.G. The paradox of irrigation efficiency // *Science*. – 2018. – Vol. 361. – No. 6404. – P. 748–750. – DOI: 10.1126/science.aat9314.
7. Hoekstra A.Y., Chapagain A.K. *Globalization of Water: Sharing the Planet's Freshwater Resources* / A.Y. Hoekstra, A.K. Chapagain. – Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, 2008. – 224 p.
8. Mekonnen M.M., Hoekstra A.Y. Four billion people facing severe water scarcity // *Science Advances*. – 2016. – Vol. 2. – No. 2. – Article e1500323. – DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.1500323.
9. Molden D. (Ed.). *Water for Food, Water for Life: A Comprehensive Assessment of Water Management in Agriculture* / D. Molden (Ed.). – London; Colombo: Earthscan; International Water Management Institute, 2007. – 645 p.
10. Porter M.E. Location, competition, and economic development: Local clusters in a global economy // *Economic Development Quarterly*. – 2000. – Vol. 14. – No. 1. – P. 15–34. – DOI: 10.1177/089124240001400105.

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 5

© When materials are reproduced, the ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

